

Vulnerable plates: What we (Don't) know about food and health

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Abstract

As part of the European Food CLIC project (2022–2027), a survey was conducted in Braşov, Romania to assess the population's health and nutrition, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups. The project aims to support the sustainable transformation of urban food systems and to raise awareness about the impact of diet on health—especially in the context of excessive consumption of fats, sugars, and food additives. The survey, carried out on a sample of 300 individuals, specifically targeted groups at high risk of food insecurity: homeless people, elderly individuals in care homes, students from disadvantaged neighborhoods, and low-income university students. The tools used were the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) model (to assess food insecurity) and the Dietary Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) model (to evaluate diet quality). The results revealed a lack of awareness about the connection between diet and serious illnesses: less than 1% of respondents associated their diet with diseases such as cancer. Similarly, only 4.3% mentioned obesity as a nutrition-related problem, while nutritional deficiencies such as anemia were more commonly cited. Another notable finding was the extremely low consumption of raw foods (only 3.3%), which may point to cultural preferences or economic barriers in accessing fresh produce. Additionally, around 8% of participants rated their own health as "poor" or "very poor," suggesting a potentially high-risk group. Misconceptions about nutrition can be a major barrier to healthier eating behaviors. The lack of awareness about the link between diet and chronic disease, the underestimation of obesity, and the preference for cooked over raw foods all highlight the urgent need for targeted nutrition education. Furthermore, identifying vulnerable groups who perceive their health negatively should prompt early interventions and the development of dedicated support programs.

Keywords: Food safety, food security, nutrition, FIES, DQQ, health care.

1. Introduction

Urban areas, home to three-quarters of Europe's population, face major challenges in ensuring access to healthy, safe, affordable, and sustainably produced food. Food poverty affects around 33 million Europeans, who cannot afford a proper meal every other day, while others lack incentives to choose sustainable diets [1-4]. Obesity is also rising, with over half of European adults overweight, leading to diet-related diseases such as diabetes and cardiovascular conditions [5]. Meanwhile, small-scale producers often struggle to earn a living wage [6,7].

The food system contributes to environmental degradation—impacting soil, water, pollinators, and biodiversity—while about 20% of food is wasted [8]. Agriculture generates 10% of EU greenhouse gas emissions, with food systems contributing 17%, a figure expected to rise if diets remain unchanged [9–11].

In urban settings, food choices are influenced by availability, cost, and appeal, yet the food environment rarely makes the healthy and sustainable choice the default [6,12].

Deprived urban areas are often overlooked by public planning and shaped mainly by market forces. This

leads residents to rely on unhealthy, highly processed foods from unsustainable food systems—characterized by carbon-intensive methods, excessive pesticide and fertilizer use, soil degradation, and neglect of animal welfare. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the fragility of such systems, which depend on long, homogenized supply chains [13].

In response, many European cities have begun rethinking food environments to improve access to local, healthy, and sustainable food [14]. Research funding has driven pilot projects that reconfigure food choices through new retail models, procurement strategies, product placement, and food marketing. However, these initiatives often fail to scale out or up and rarely involve vulnerable groups meaningfully [15]. Barriers include space competition, conflicting interests, limited funding, and counterproductive fiscal and advertising policies.

Scaling successful pilots requires stronger policy and planning support. Although food has gained some attention in urban policy, planning systems largely exclude it, focusing instead on land, housing, and infrastructure. Urban food policies must be better integrated with planning tools like zoning

laws to support sustainable food access [16]. Planners should become “food sensitive,” recognizing food’s ties to public health, environmental sustainability, and well-being.

Most cities still struggle to build integrated food-planning frameworks. Often, not all three sustainability goals (social/health, economic, environmental) or Food 2030 priorities (health, climate, circularity, inclusion) are addressed. Policies lack stakeholder support and empirical evidence [17-22], and siloed approaches limit understanding of local food systems. Key stakeholders—including citizens, civil society, experts, and businesses—are underrepresented, hampering broader and deeper food system transformation.

In this context, the FOODCLIC project, in which the city of Braşov is part of the consortium, has among its objectives an assessment focused on nutrition and health. This initiative aims to raise awareness about the impact of diet on health, addressing the risks associated with modern eating habits, such as excessive consumption of saturated fats, refined sugars, and additives. The activity is particularly focused on vulnerable populations, including residents of disadvantaged neighborhoods like Noua and Bartolomeu Nord, students from local schools (School No. 9 and School No. 14), and elderly individuals in care homes. It seeks to improve nutritional education by distributing informative brochures, monographs, and leaflets, which are developed in collaboration with the faculties of Food and Tourism and Medicine.

A series of activities support this initiative, such as educational campaigns in schools, partnerships with local food markets, and events like the nutrition-focused research symposium scheduled for September 2024. The program also includes hands-on learning through an educational greenhouse at School No. 14 and guided visits to farms and hypermarkets to enhance food literacy. These efforts align with the broader strategy to address the lack of nutritional education in Braşov, ensuring the participation of local authorities, schools, businesses, and healthcare institutions in promoting healthier food choices and improving food security in the city.

The data was collected through individual surveys, to a total number of 300 male and female participants. For the questionnaires we have used the FIES model to determine the food insecurity of participants and for dietary quality, we used the DQQ model. We did not choose to include further methods like food diaries or questionnaires for food literacy.

2. Material and method

The study sample consisted of 300 participants. Regarding age distribution, the largest age group was those between 8 and 17 years old,

making up 33.3% of the sample. Participants aged 18 to 24 years accounted for 25.3%, those aged 25 to 44 years represented 7.7%, while 14.7% were aged 45 to 64 years, and 19% were over 65 years old. In terms of gender, the sample was fairly balanced, with 52% female and 48% male participants

The sampling strategy used was a mix of purposive sampling and convenience sampling, because:

1. We intentionally targeted vulnerable populations (e.g. homeless individuals, institutionalized elderly, schoolchildren in underserved areas, and low-income university students).
2. We selected specific locations (Noua and Bartolomeu neighborhood), where these groups could be accessed directly (e.g. church, elderly home, schools, canteen).
3. Within these locations, we selected participants based on availability and willingness to respond, which adds a convenience sampling element.

We had 300 participants, and the selection of them was made in order to ensure that 80% are vulnerable. We have:

- 50 institutionalized respondents in the Noua neighborhood Elderly Home;
- We have 50 people which every Thursday eat at a Social Canteen organized by an NGO in collaboration with an orthodox church, and almost all of these participants are homeless;
- We have 50 pupils from Bartolomeu neighborhood school no. 14;
- We have 50 pupils from Noua neighborhood school no. 9;
- We have 50 students from Memorandului dormitory, which eat all their meals at the student canteen from Bartolomeu neighbourhood;
- And we have 50 randomly selected participants, whom were invited to respond to our survey from both Noua and Bartolomeu neighbourhood, during our recent food walks.

We aimed for gender balance during the data collection process by being intentional about who we approached in each setting. While working in different locations (church, elderly home, schools, and university canteen), we made efforts to include a diverse mix of participants, paying attention to gender representation.

Romanian legislation does not allow us to make payments to respondents or to buy goods for them. However, when it was possible, we made efforts to recompensate them in collaboration with different sponsors that offer them free fruits/vegetables, sponsor that are also stakeholders, part of our Brasov FPN.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Self-perceived health

The biometric analysis of the respondents shows a large variation in the reported weight and height values, which indicates the existence of significant individual differences. Heights ranged between 120 cm and 197 cm, and weights between 30 kg and 120 kg, a range that suggests the presence of both possibly underweight and overweight or obese people in the sample. These extremes may influence the perception of one's own health - for example, those with very low or very high weights could assess their general condition differently. The subjective assessment is explainable because the target groups in disadvantaged areas have a modest social status or extreme ages, i.e. schoolchildren (56.7%) or pensioners (19.7%), of course also with precarious monthly incomes, 48% having less than 2000 lei (400 euros).

Regarding the type and level of food, it is noted that from a quantitative point of view there are no problems (at least three meals/day), and from a food quality perspective, its association with the relatively limited possibilities of purchasing more expensive and therefore higher quality food is relevant (27.5% under 200 euros/month, or 48% under 400 euros/month, approximately half of the respondents). We would like to point out that in Romania, a person could survive on approximately 500-700 euros per month, depending on location and lifestyle. In large cities, costs may be higher, but in rural areas, they may be lower.

However, paradoxically, the perception of one's own health is not described as "bad", but rather as "satisfactory" (positive), which denotes a lack of realism and a poor food culture of the target groups and, respectively, becomes more than an obstacle to placing additional emphasis on education (especially among schoolchildren).

The response of those surveyed regarding lifestyle supports the idea of information on nutrition mentioned above, as the figures suggest that the vast majority of participants do not have a constant routine regarding that aspect of lifestyle (whether it is physical activity, weight monitoring or other health-related habit). The data (Brasov LL survey) show that only a very small percentage adopt certain beneficial behaviours on a daily basis (such as regular physical exercise or constant consumption of healthy foods). Moreover, regarding the connection between food and lifestyle and non-lifestyle, only 21.7% show the convergence of this connection. The numbers suggest that the participants do not have a consistent routine for that aspect of their lifestyle (whether it's physical activity, weight monitoring, or another health-related habit). This lack of regularity can, over time, affect the perception of one's own health and even one's actual health status.

An eloquent aspect of the schoolchildren's eating habits results from the fact that most of them are directly linked to family food (49.3% eat with

the family and 43.7% eat during breaks from the home-made package. We deduce that it would be a good control of the health status through the family eating habits. Unfortunately, we find that there is no clear awareness of the connection between nutrition and possible diseases. On the other hand, the answers given show the lack of awareness of nutritional deficiencies, both among schoolchildren and the elderly. Therefore, the results regarding the perception of health indicate a moderate optimism of the respondents towards their own condition, but also possible hidden problems - for example, the approximately 8% who declare themselves in a precarious condition could represent vulnerable groups (perhaps elderly people or with chronic diseases) that require attention. In addition, the underestimation of obesity as a problem suggests the need for education: if the risks of obesity and other diseases associated with diet are not well known, people would not take preventive measures.

As an argument we see that 38.3% prefer cooking by frying in oil and 61% "nibble" something all the time (sweets, biscuits, chips, etc.) without taking into account digestion and do not value information related to the quality of food (only 17.3% take into account audio-visual information).

This results in a solution to be followed, i.e. a useful action would be to carry out local awareness campaigns regarding the effects of unbalanced nutrition on health (for example, the link with obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases), as well as promoting an active lifestyle. Also, given that only a small proportion declares healthy daily habits, programs to encourage regular physical activity and healthy eating habits (such as daily breakfast or meals at fixed times) could improve both the objective state of health and its perception in the long term.

The aspects regarding the perception of one's own health are a complex concept, which, as we have seen from the survey, is not based only on the objective physical state, but also on psychological, social and cultural factors. A correct and objective self-assessment can lead to proactive behavior regarding the prevention and treatment of diseases and requires mandatory schooling in the direction of forming a good food culture, especially among young people.

3.2. Food (In)security

It is obvious that food insecurity is a global problem that refers to the lack of constant and sufficient access to safe and nutritious food to lead an active and healthy life. What is important is that by analysing the causes (economic, political, social and environmental factors) it is found important to consider these factors at the local level in order to find solutions to solve their causes because they

directly influence the availability and accessibility of food for individuals and implicitly for communities.

The data provided by the survey shows that, even in the target groups of the project (schoolchildren from disadvantaged neighbourhood's or institutionalized elderly people) the food situation is not desperate, that is, we are not talking about severe food insecurity, but about moderate food insecurity. In the situation analysed in Braşov, it is characterized by reduced accessibility to quality food, which can lead to inadequate nutrition and a compromised state of health. The people surveyed are affected by moderate food insecurity during periods when they do not have enough food, but do not reach the point of suffering from severe malnutrition.

Among the causes of the respondents' food insecurity phases, we find economic and social inequality, relative poverty and limited access to education and health services. Hence the increase in social vulnerability with the increase in inequalities in certain situations, especially in terms of food quality. The survey data provide indications regarding the respondents' access to sufficient food and the regularity of meals, and certain patterns can be observed that may signal food insecurity or at least irregular eating habits. For example, for 95% of the participants, there are days when they skip meals or

do not follow a strict eating schedule. This can be caused either by time constraints (busy lifestyle) or by lack of appetite in the morning, but it can also indicate difficulties in procuring or preparing food regularly – a possible sign of moderate food insecurity.

Another set of relevant findings concerns how people procure and consume their daily food. Eating “on the run” (meals eaten in a hurry, perhaps outside the home or without sitting down) is reported by a minority of the sample – only 5.7% of respondents indicated that they usually eat “on the run”. This relatively low percentage can have two interpretations: either most have the opportunity to eat meals in peace (at home or at the institution where they work), or many skip meals altogether when they are busy, instead of eating on the run. Given that only 5% have a consistent daily eating habit, it is possible that some do not eat at all during busy times, which is also a form of food insecurity (when their work schedule or financial situation does not allow for regular meals).

Regarding financial constraints, those with lower incomes or precarious situations (fig. 3.1) show that this percentage of 21% is not very significant, but suggests a potential limited access to culinary variety or convenient eating options, making it possible to skip meals.

33. You had to skip a meal because there was not enough money or other resources to get food?
300 responses

Fig. 3.1. Financial structure in relation to the inadvisability of skipping meals

Another aspect highlighted by the respondents' answers refers to the diversity of eating habits among the participants, which leaves a bit to be desired. Reference is made to the reduced consumption of raw foods and/or protective foods (fruits, fresh vegetables, fish), which indicates a diet that could be unbalanced. Even if home-cooked food predominates (which is often good), what and how is cooked is important in terms of quality. But the encouraging fact is that about 80% of the respondents did not have problems with various diseases or conditions (fig.3.2).

In order to completely remove food insecurity from the analysis of the questionnaires, although the problem is not serious, it potentially exists, so solutions and measures are required to

combat and completely avoid food insecurity, of which we propose the following: - Increasing access to financial resources: Economic policies that support people with low incomes and improving general economic conditions can help reduce food insecurity, such as improving infrastructure and food distribution by creating a more equitable and efficient food distribution system that reaches vulnerable people, can reduce inequalities in access to food; - Supporting sustainable agriculture: Investments in sustainable agricultural practices and technologies that help increase food production, especially in regions vulnerable to climate change, can help ensure greater access to food; - Social protection measures: Social assistance programs, such as meal vouchers, free school meals or direct

financial support for vulnerable families, can help reduce food insecurity; - Nutrition education and promotion of healthy eating: Education on choosing a balanced diet and the importance of healthy eating can help people make better choices even when resources are limited. Food insecurity is a complex and multidimensional issue that requires a coordinated response from governments, international organizations, the private sector and civil society to ensure that every person has access to adequate and nutritious food.

39. Are you aware of any of the following diseases?
 300 responses

Fig. 3.2. Health status structure and presence of conditions or diseases

3.3 Dietary Diversity

The diversity of food habits reflects the various cultures, traditions and geographies of the world. Each society has its own food-related practices, influenced by factors such as religion,

climate, natural resources, but also socio-economic history. In this context, from the survey conducted, I have identified several aspects that highlight the diversity of food habits that we also encounter in the Braşov area: food habits according to age and social status, food according to culture, religion, traditions and meal habits, cultural holiday traditions. Diversification of food sources (including trying new or more varied foods) should be encouraged – perhaps through local events, accessible fresh produce markets or even partnerships with restaurants offering healthy menus at reduced prices, to accustom the population to other types of food. The aim would be for eating habits to become more varied and balanced, thus preventing nutritional deficiencies and diseases associated with a monotonous diet. In this regard, the survey shows that foods specific to the area were consumed, being of a diverse nature, both plant and animal (figures 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5).

3.4 Recommendations

Based on these findings, food education programs that encourage dietary diversification would be useful. For example, campaigns that promote daily consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables (“5 a day”) could increase the current very low percentage (5%) of daily consumers. Also, the initiation of healthy cooking workshops in the community, which could show a number of ways to prepare vegetables in an attractive way, so that people consume them more often fresh. Because many prefer traditional cooked foods, more vegetables and lean proteins could be integrated into these recipes, while reducing fried foods and excess salt, especially for older adults and those who live longer (over 75 years).

42. Yesterday, did you eat any of the following vegetables:

Fig. 3.3. Consumed Plant foods

43. Yesterday, did you eat any of the following fruits:

Fig. 3.4. Proportion of fruit consumption or lack of consumption

45. Yesterday, did you eat any of the following foods of animal origin:

Fig. 3.5. Consumption of animal origin foods

4. Conclusions

Food insecurity is a complex and multidimensional problem that requires a coordinated response from central and local governments (municipalities), international organizations, the private sector and civil society to ensure that every person has access to adequate and nutritious food. Overall, the survey undertaken on healthy eating revealed new perspectives, but also challenges and conflicts, which makes this field a constantly changing and sometimes quite surprising one, which requires permanent adaptation at the local level. The Braşov survey provides a valuable insight into the population's food behaviours and perceptions, along lines that highlight elements with certain strengths – for example, the majority do not consider themselves to be in very poor health, and very few seem to depend on unhealthy food in the city. Another aspect of the survey reveals a set of problems and deficiencies, such as a monotonous diet, poor in fresh vegetables/fruits, irregular meals and some misconceptions about nutrition. Addressing these problems requires concerted actions (education, public health interventions) and, at the same time, continuous monitoring. The research indicates that there is an important diversity of food habits in Braşov, such as how traditions and cultural context influence daily life, which indicates the exploration of practices that can provide a deeper understanding of how people interact with their environment and with each other, in the context of the Braşov city-region. By improving both the knowledge of the population and the research tools, future surveys will be able to track progress and better guide public policies, for the benefit of the health of the Braşov community regarding food safety and quality food, especially when it comes to vulnerable consumer groups, such as schoolchildren and the elderly. These groups are more susceptible to the risks associated with unhealthy diets and low-quality products, and protective measures must be taken seriously in future local actions and policies.

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